

PROCESS DESIGN CONCEPT FOR AUTOMATED PRE-ASSEMBLING OF MULTI-MATERIAL PREFORMS

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ABSTRACT

In order to increase the economic potential of light-weight components, the specific combination of different materials in one component is aspired. This multi-material design follows the approach of using the right material at the right place for the best function of the manufactured component. This results in two main advantages: On the one hand, the multi-material approach enables functional specific light-weight design. On the other hand, in comparison to pure fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP), costs can be saved by specific material substitution.

A key requirement to force the way of (multi-material) lightweight constructions and design into automotive large-scale production is a continuous and automated process chain. A production process with a considerable industrialization potential is the combined thermoforming and injection molding of thermoplastic FRP blanks. Besides the single processes of heating and shaping, the automated linking between them is of high importance. At this, the properties of the processed materials represent multiple automation challenges, especially the reliable handling of limp, tacky and fast cooling heated thermoplastic FRP blanks. These material properties differ from conventionally processed materials in the automotive sector, such as metal, which is solid, non-tacky and cools much slower than thermoplastics. The use of both materials in one component offers the potential of affecting not only the properties of the final component, but also the manufacturing itself.

This paper introduces a proposal for an integrative approach in automated manufacturing of multi-material components by benefitting from the combination of different materials in an early step of the process chain. Instead of handling several work pieces separately and inserting into the molding tool, a multi-material preform is manufactured in an upstream pre-assembly process step and transferred as well as processed as one unit. In this paper the positive effects on the thermal behavior of the materials during handling operations are demonstrated.

1 INTRODUCTION

The application of conventional metal-based lightweight strategies, to open up further weight saving potential and high volume markets in automotive sector, reaches its economic limits. Furthermore, fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) are no economic alternative for volume markets because of their high material and manufacturing costs yet.

With the objective of increasing the economic potential of light-weight components, the specific combination of different materials in one component is aspired. This multi-material design follows the approach of using the right material at the right place for the best function of the manufactured component [1][2]. Through a specific material combination, the advantages of the separate material properties can be used. This results in two main advantages: On the one hand, the multi-material approach enables functional specific lightweight design. On the other hand, in comparison to pure FRP lightweight design, costs can be saved by targeted material substitution [3].

There are two main different manufacturing routes for manufacturing multi-material components. They differ in the point of merging the materials (Figure 1): The first one is to manufacture several parts

of different materials with material-specific production technologies separately. Afterwards the parts are joined by adhesives or mechanical joining techniques in downstream assembling processes to get a multi-material component. Depending on the complexity of the component and the amount of parts, the subsequent assembling is very expensive.

In the second route, different materials are combined in an earlier stage of the manufacturing process and are processed jointly. This manufacturing route is an intrinsic, at best a one-shot process. The joining of the different materials is achieved during shaping and molding processes in a molding tool. Therefore, additional joining operations in a downstream assembling process are not necessary, which saves time and costs.

Figure 1: Two main different manufacturing routes to produce multi-material components [4]

Due to the mostly conventional material-specific oriented plant concepts, an economical manufacturing of integrated multi-material components in large-scale quantity is not feasible yet. Therefore, conventional process routes and plant concepts are to be expanded, to allow manufacturing of appropriate component complexities and ensure a high degree of automation in a continuous process chain. [5]-[7]

In this paper, the authors discuss the automation challenges with focus on handling operations in processing plate-shaped continuous fiber-reinforced thermoplastic and show current solutions. Further, they introduce an integrative approach in automated manufacturing of multi-material components by benefitting of the combination of plate-shaped continuous fiber-reinforced thermoplastics and metallic components. The use of both materials in one component offers the potential of affecting not only the properties of the final component, but also the manufacturing itself. In addition, results of the thermal and handling behavior of the materials during handling operations are demonstrated.

2 AUTOMATION CHALLENGES IN PROCESSING THERMOPLASTIC FRP BLANKS

A production technology of producing FRP components with a considerable industrialization potential is the manufacturing of thermoplastic-based components [8][9]. In contrast to resin-based technologies, this technology processes plate-shaped, tailored, pre-impregnated and consolidated fabrics with thermoplastic matrices (TP-FRP) as raw material. The TP-FRP blank is heated in an oven (mostly infrared or convection) and then processed after transferring into a molding tool in a combined thermoforming and injection molding process. The result is a shaped thermoplastic FRP component with injected functional elements, e.g. fins [10][11]. The processing bases on the combination of already large scale-ready technologies of sheet metal forming and thermoplastic injection molding.

Current developments of TP-FRP processing technologies provide first automation solutions to produce pure FRP components in an almost continuous process chain. TP-FRP cut-outs are automatically placed in an oven, removed, transferred and inserted into the mold [12][13]. However, despite of intensive research, the implementation of FRP has not taken place in high volume production, yet. Next to the high material costs, especially missing automation solutions for the required reliable handling operations during or between single process steps are the reason for this.

2.1 Material properties and resulting handling requirements

The difficulties that arise in the development of automated and continuous process chains are mainly due to the properties and the resulting behavior of the used thermoplastic FRP blanks. The material properties differ from conventional processed materials in the automotive sector, such as metal.

The material behavior of fabrics with impregnated thermoplastic matrix is uncritical as long as the temperature is below the melting temperature of the matrix material. In this state, the TP-FRP blanks have a bending stiffness, which is sufficient to ensure a defined geometry and position during handling operations. Moreover, the surface of the material is solid and flat. Handling operations can be performed by using standard vacuum grippers without any special features.

To enable processing the solid TP-FRP blanks in a molding process, the matrix must be heated above its melting temperature. Due to fusing, the bending stiffness of the TP-FRP blanks loses the proportion of the matrix material and only the very low bending stiffness of the fabric remains. That results in a limp behavior. This limp behavior is advantageous for shaping, but there is the danger of damaging several fibers or losing their orientation in the composite. Moreover, because of the melted matrix material, the surface of the blank becomes tacky and uneven. The melted condition lasts only for a short time slot after stopping the heating process due to the fast cooling of the thin-walled materials. [13][14]

By means of the described material properties and behavior of melted TP-FRP blanks, the following requirements for gripping and handling operations can be derived:

(1) To ensure a reliable positioning process and prevent sag of the heated TP-FRP blanks during gripping, transport and dropping, an adequate support of the limp material is required. Depending on the complexity of the blanks, the configuration (amount and layout of gripping components) of the handling structure must be adjusted.

(2) The tacky surface is a danger of damaging the TP-FRP blanks (due to removing matrix material) and causes wear of gripping components because of adhesion (due to remaining matrix material). Thus, the contact areas between the tacky object and the gripper must be designed non-adhesive.

(3) The low heat capacity of the thin-walled blanks results in fast heat dissipation by conduction at the gripping points and convection due to additional air stream during handling movements. It is necessary to ensure that the heated TP-FRP blank does not cool down below its melting temperature during the transport operation between oven and mold, as this causes damage of the processes blank and consequently of the final component. Depending on the process and hardware design, process times for handling, transport and dropping of 10 s are realistic.

2.2 State of the art handling approaches and solutions

To meet the described requirements of reliable handling of heated TP-FRP blanks, different equipment approaches are pursued. To meet the gripping requirements, three main categories of grippers are usually applied (Figure 2):

Figure 2: Needle gripper (a), clamping tenter frame (b) and vacuum gripper (c) for handling of heated TP-FRP-blanks

A typical gripping principle for limp fabrics is provided by needle grippers [15]. During melted condition, angular arranged needles penetrate the blank and hold it by form fit. Handling suppliers, such as Schmalz and ASS, offer application adjusted needle grippers with non-adhesive and thermal isolated contact areas to reduce matrix adhesion and cooling by conduction. The low contact between the gripper

needles and the blank are advantageous with regard to cooling. Conversely, the disadvantage of this gripping principle is the punctuation of the fabric, which could cause damage by moving the fibers.

Another handling principle is a tenter frame. The cut-out is fixed by clamps or hooks at the outer contour and tensioned by springs in solid state. For heating the TP-FRP blank, the entire frame is moved into an infrared oven. The springs prevent sag while fusing [16]. After heating, the frame is positioned between the mold halves. Because the blank is not dropped onto the mold, contact between TP-FRP blank and mold, which causes early cooling, is prevented. A tenter frame with adaptive tension kinematic is offered by ASS. The main disadvantages of a clamp-based tenter frame are the high space requirement and the missing heating at the clamping areas because of shading the heat radiation. These areas are not processible. Therefore, a wraparound edge is left outside the mold. This fact causes blend.

The third gripping principle is gripping by vacuum. E.g. Schmalz and Gimatic offer high temperature proof vacuum components for handling heated TP-FRP blanks. The suction bags of the grippers are designed flat and have a supporting structure to prevent local deformation of the blank in the gripping area. Contact areas made of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and fluorinated elastomers (FKM) prevent adhesion between gripper and object as well as cooling. A danger of this gripping principle is an air flow due to possible leakage between the gripper and the blank. This causes early cooling in the gripping area.

3 PRE-ASSEMBLING APPROACH OF MULTI-MATERIAL-PREFORMS

3.1 Potential processing benefits of an early material combination

The automation challenges explained in the previous section result from the processing of pure TP-FRP blanks. As described in the introduction, multi-material lightweight design aspired the specific combination of different materials in one component to get the best function of the manufactured component. In addition to the properties and functions, that the different materials meet in the manufactured component, the materials also behave differently in the manufacturing process.

A typical material combination of a shell-shaped multi-material component consists of TP-FRP blanks and metal on- and inserts. Due to partially contrary properties (bending stiffness, adhesion, heat capacity) of these materials in heated state (Table 1), there is the potential of benefitting from a material combination by influencing the properties or rather the behavior of the material during the manufacturing process.

Material property	TP-FRP	Metal
<i>Bending stiffness</i>	low	high
<i>Adhesion</i>	high	low
<i>Heat capacity</i>	low	high

Table 1: Contrary material properties of TP-FRP and metal in processible state [4]

It is assumed, that a specific combination of materials with contrary properties und behavior during the manufacturing process can influence the handling properties and the local heat management.

(1) To meet the requirements of reliable handling, a handling tool must offer a sufficient number of grippers to ensure geometry and position of the transferred object. The areal size of the gripper is at least equal to the size of the blank. With increasing object size, the size of the handling tool, the number of grippers and the complexity of the gripper layout increases. Metal support structures in a multi-material component influence the local bending stiffness and may therefore simplify the handling.

(2) Moreover, metallic parts in the component provide stiff and non-tacky areas, which may be used as gripping points. This may reduce the danger of material damage and wear of gripper. Blend may be

reduced. In addition, stiff and non-tacky areas enable a larger selection of gripping principles than described in section 2.2. It may be feasible to use further standard gripping components like clamping or magnetic grippers.

(3) Metal parts in the component can influence the low heat capacity of the thin TP-FRP blanks. Temperature dissipation may be decreased locally in the contact area between blank and gripper. This would enable longer handling and processing times.

3.1 Process concept

To benefit from the above mentioned assumptions, the combination of the different materials must be made before the critical handling process between the oven and the mold, as long as the TP-FRP blank is solid. Therefore, a pre-assembling process for multi-material preforms was developed by the authors (Figure 3). The pre-assembling process is embedded into a combined thermoforming and injection molding process: TP-FRP blanks and metal parts are pre-assembled and fixed in solid state. Afterwards, the assembled multi-material preform is transferred into an oven. There, it is heated above the melting temperature of the matrix material and then transferred as one unit into the molding tool, where the component reaches its final contour and strength due to shaping and injection molding.

Figure 3: Material properties during the pre-assembling process of TP-FRP and metal inserts

4 FEASIBILITY STUDIES ON HANDLING AND THERMAL BEHAVIOUR OF MULTI-MATERIAL PREFORMS

For the purpose of confirmation the hypothesized and described benefits by pre-assembling and processing multi-material preforms, first feasibility tests about influencing the mechanical behavior (shape accuracy, handling properties) and the thermal behavior (heat management) are described by the authors in [4] and [17]. These studies are extended in this paper by further investigations on thermal behavior during the handling process of a heated multi-material preform. Especially investigations on the cooling behavior of varying pure TP-FRP blanks and TP-FRP-metal combination (varying thickness of TP-FRP) and handling parameters (different gripping principles) were performed. The objective was to achieve an adequate understanding of thermodynamics regarding the material behavior during the handling process.

4.1 Setup and process

For the purpose of carrying out the investigations, the handling process between heating device and molding tool was built up in laboratory scale. In order to ensure the reproducibility of the results, the investigations were carried out in an automated heating and handling process. The schematical set-up and process are shown in Figure 4, left. The material supply provides TP-FRP blanks at ambient temperature of 20 °C and steel force input elements, which are previously heated on a controlled heating plate. For heating the TP-FRP blanks, a controlled infrared heating unit with fast medium-wave IR emitters is installed. An articulated robot serves as a handling device. The end effector of the robot is fitted with needle grippers, vacuum grippers and a magnetic gripper. It allows the use of different gripping

principles in one set-up. Needle and vacuum grippers are used to handle the heated TP-FRP blanks. The magnetic gripper is used to handle the force input elements. The individual gripping components are equipped with thermocouples in the contact area. Thus, the surface temperature of the handling objects can be recorded and the thermal behavior of the handling objects can be compared depending on the gripping principle used.

The investigations were performed with material combinations of continuous glass fiber reinforced PA6 (organic sheet, twill weave, thickness from 0.5 to 2 mm) and steel load input elements (thread bolts with 1.3 mm thick ground plate) (Figure 5, left).

Figure 4: left: Experimental set-up for measuring thermal behavior of heated TP-FRP blanks and metal inserts, right: Different temperature areas during the handling process

In order to investigate both the behavior of the individual semi-finished products as well as their combination, two process variants were defined. In the test sequence, the load input elements are heated on the heating plate to a temperature of 300 °C. After the target temperature has been reached, they are placed in the IR-oven together with a TP-FRP blank at room temperature (20 °C). For the separate investigation, the semi-finished products are placed one beside the other (a), for the purpose of a joint investigation, they are pre-assembled one above each other (b) (Figure 5, left). After storage in the IR-oven, heating is started. The individual semi-finished products and the TP-FRP-metal composite are heated to a surface temperature of about 300 °C. Subsequently, the oven is opened and the semi-finished products and the material composite are removed by the handling tool. During the process, the surface temperatures of the semi-finished products are measured at the non-gripped area (contact to ambient air at 20 °C) and the gripped areas (contact to gripper components (Figure 4, right).

Figure 5: left: Multi-material sample consisting of TP-FRP blank and steel load input element, right: Handling of multi-material sample with a magnetic gripper

4.2 Thermal behavior of separate materials (a)

Firstly, the results of the material specific investigations are demonstrated. In the following section, the recorded temperature curves of the objects removed from the oven after heating are shown. Figure 6 shows the comparison of cooling times of TP-FRP blanks with thickness from 0.5 to 2.0 mm and a steel metal inserts with thickness of 1.3 mm at ambient temperature of 20 °C. This behavior corresponds to the area of the semi-finished products which does not have any contact with the gripper during the handling process.

Figure 6: Cooling times of TP-FRP blanks and steel element at ambient temperature of 20°C

Figure 7: Cooling times of TP-FRP blanks during gripper contact

The cooling time of the investigated organic sheets from $T_{\text{Start}} = 300\text{ °C}$ to the solidification temperature of 220 °C is 15 s for 0.5 mm thickness, 27 s for 1.0 mm thickness and 2.0 s for 56 s. In comparison, the cooling behavior of the metal insert used is shown. The cooling time from 290 °C to 220 °C is 36 s. This results in the following averaged cooling rates $\Delta T/\Delta t$ of 5.3 K/s (0.5 mm), 3.0 K/s (1.0 mm) and 1.4 K/s (2 mm) for the organic sheets and 1.6 K/s for the metal inserts. The investigated cooling times correspond to the maximum time window in which the TP-FRP blanks are processible after removing them out of the oven without contact to a handling device.

In Figure 7 the cooling behavior of heated organic sheet (300 °C) in contact with different grippers (metal and isolated needle gripper and vacuum grippers) can be seen. The gripper temperature was 20 °C . Measuring was started when the organic sheet and gripper had first contact.

The different initial temperatures of the curves show, that the first contact results in fast cooling, before the handling process has started. Only the isolated needle gripper and the PTFE vacuum gripper reach start temperatures near or above 260 °C . Organic sheet with 0.5 mm thickness solidifies within 1 to 2 s when gripping it by vacuum. Longest cooling times are reached with 2.0 mm organic sheet handled with isolated needle gripper. Time till solid state takes about 26 s.

4.3 Thermal behavior of multi-material combination (b)

In the following, the measurement results of the material combination of TP-FRP blank and steel force input element are illustrated. The temperature curves were recorded while a magnetic gripper moved the material combination as a unit. As it can be seen in Figure 8, the cooling time of the material combination after heating until solidification temperature of 220 °C is 13 s at 0.5 mm and 26 s at 1.0 mm organic sheet.

Figure 8: Cooling time of TP-FRP blank in combination with metal insert on a magnetic gripper

4.4 Comparison

In Figure 9 the cooling times from start temperature of 300 °C to solidification temperature of 220 °C are shown in comparison, depending on material thickness of the TP-FRP blank and the contact medium. For the process-safe gripping of the material from the oven, transport, placing in the mold and closing of the press, a time window of 10 s is assumed. This value must not be exceeded.

The reference time is the cooling time of the pure TP-FRP blanks at ambient air. This represents the maximum feasible processing time without any gripper contact within areas of the cut-out (e.g. tenter frame), that must be shaped, as well as without additional heating during handling.

It is recognizable that this time is reduced, if the heated blank comes in contact with gripping components. In worst case, a vacuum gripper causes fast cooling of pure TP-FRP blank within 1 to 2 s caused by leakage. These negative effects especially occur at the thin TP-FRP blanks with 0.5 and 1.0 mm thickness, because of their low thermal mass. They are almost not processible without additional heating during handling, if grippers are placed within functional areas. Even though the cooling times of 2.0 mm blanks are reduced, the required assumed processing time of 10 s is achieved by most of the grippers.

Figure 9: Cooling times of TP-FRP blanks depending on contact with ambient air and grippers

If the thin sheets are gripped in areas with a metallic insert (multi-material sample), the cooling time is hardly affected compared to the contact with air. The time window is reduced by only 1 to 2 s. Even the 0.5 mm blanks need 13 s to cool below 220°C. These values are within the range of the cooling times of the TP-FRP blanks at ambient air (without gripper contact). Therefore, the investigations show that the combination of the materials in conjunction with a magnetic gripper does not reduce feasible processing time of heated TP-FRP blanks. This has a positive effect on the available processing time.

5 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Against the background of an economical production of multi-material lightweight components, this article described the automation challenges and requirements in handling of fiber-reinforced thermoplastic blanks. Besides available handling equipment solutions, a proposal for an integrative approach in automated manufacturing of multi-material components was introduced. At this, the different materials are pre-assembled at an early stage of the production process. It was hypothesized, that a component integrated material combination may not only lead to influencing the properties of the final component, but also the properties during automated manufacturing processes.

For this purpose, the influence of material combinations, material thickness and contact to ambient air or different kind of grippers on the thermal behavior of heated TP-FRP was investigated. The results showed that the use of conventional gripper technology significantly reduces the handling times or the maximum possible processing times of heated TP-FRP blanks, if the handling areas on the organic sheet lie within the later component. The handling times can be extended by increasing the heat capacity locally by metallic inserts. This is particularly advantageous in the case of thin organic sheets. The use of metallic components also makes it feasible to apply gripping principles which extend the conventional textile gripper solutions. In the research carried out, this was confirmed by a magnetic gripper which handled a multi-material sample.

Future work will continue to deal with the thermal behavior of multi-material preforms. In addition, the mechanical properties during the handling procedures are examined. The research objective will be to provide support for efficient product and process design for automated manufacturing of multi-material components.

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